

Protocol for the Systematic Review: Evaluation of Postpartum Depression Strategies Based on Primary Care

Objective:

Identify and evaluate the strategies implemented in primary health care for the prevention, detection, and management of postpartum depression.

Review Question:

What strategies have been applied in primary health care settings to prevent, detect, or manage postpartum depression in women during the postpartum period?

Eligibility Criteria:

- Population: Postpartum women.
- Setting: Primary health care.
- Study designs: Clinical trials, observational studies, systematic reviews, guidelines, quasi-experimental studies.
- Time frame: 2020–2025.
- Language: English or Spanish.
- Exclusion: Studies not focused on primary care, irrelevant populations, or lacking outcomes on postpartum depression.

Search Strategy:

Searches will be conducted in PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, SciELO, and LILACS using predefined terms related to postpartum depression and primary care.

Data Extraction and Synthesis:

Data will be extracted based on study design, interventions, outcomes, and measurement tools. A narrative synthesis will be conducted; no meta-analysis is planned.

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